

Distributed BSP control methods for underwater collective manipulation

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Abstract—We have developed a novel cooperative manipulation approach exploiting the compliance of the 'grippers' and a Reynolds boids' collective coordinated movement implemented, by exploiting Belief Space Planning (BSP) to enforce the Reynolds' flock rules.

Index Terms—swarm of underwater robots, collective intelligence, cooperative autonomous grasping and transportation

I. INTRODUCTION

We address the topic of underwater manipulation and transportation, using a novel methodology: we propose a control strategy based on BSP (Belief Space Planning) control and a simple extension of Reynolds' boids to perform underwater grasping and transportation tasks by means of tick-like robots remarkably smaller than the object to be transported.

Many projects tried to demonstrate underwater manipulation, first from a fixed base like in AMADEUS [5] and ROBUST [14], and then with a robotic arm onboard a ROV/AUV, like SAUVIM [9] and TRIDENT [13]. Cooperative manipulation was addressed by the Italian PRIN MARIS [6]. A dual-arm manipulator was controlled through an exoskeleton in DexROV [7]. The ongoing SEACLEAR project [1] is developing a system to collect marine litter; however, they employ a single underwater vehicle equipped with a gripper working as a cage to trap the target objects. All the cited works clearly show the limitations and constraints of traditional systems with bulky robots and long kinematic chains. The research work here presented is conducted within the context of the BEASTIE (roBotic undErwater Autonomous Social Team for cooperative manipulation and Intelligence) project, funded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research.

The BEASTIE aim consists in pursuing a new, disruptive concept in underwater soft manipulation for a wide range of applications, by eliminating the constraints given by cooperation of multiple physical kinematic chains focusing on the issue of controlling a morphing multi-body supra-manipulator constituted by single-link agents connected through virtual

links. The manipulation capability can be pursued by a team of small floating robots, able to communicate and cooperate together to accomplish the desired task. Each robot is constituted by a very simple soft gripper and a body, equipped with suitable actuators and sensors to support its motion, with no kinematic chains or joints in-between. The robot body should be able to: i) reach the target object; ii) allow grasping and manipulation of objects. Figure 1 shows a pictorial representation of the BEASTIE concept.

Underwater cooperative control is challenging because the environment in which the robots operate is only partially known, complex and time-varying. Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) [17], [10], [8] endows each agent with the ability to learn new behaviors online, to gradually improve performance, through a trial-and-error process by interactions with the environment and the other present agents. However, these systems are complex, computationally and for their setting up. Recently swarm management methodologies based on a Reynolds' boids implementation and Belief Space Planning have been proposed [2], [4]. Here, we focus on the control strategy for cooperative navigation and grasping, by exploiting this last approach.

In section II the overall methodology followed in our research is described, section III outlines in more detail the BSP control characteristics, and results are presented and discussed in section IV. Finally, section V draws the conclusive remarks.

II. METHODOLOGY

Robots are endowed with 6 DoF-motion skills in water, and are able to communicate and cooperate together to accomplish the required tasks. As said, they are constituted by a very simple soft gripper and a body, equipped with suitable actuators and sensors to support its 6 DoFs motion in the underwater space (complete attitude control), with no kinematic chains or joints in-between. The gripper has a camera in the palm, and is built with soft materials to gain compliance in order to guarantee the preservation of fragile samplings. Softness also improves grasping stability by adapting the grippers of the different robots during the cooperative manipulation task.

Swarm control is obtained by making the robots converge toward the swarm estimated center of mass (where the object

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Fig. 1: Pictorial representation of the BEASTIE concept.

to be grasped is), grasping together the object and then keeping a safety distance among them. Robots' softness and deformable smart materials make possible the concurrent task of keeping a safety distance among the swarm agents and not loosing the grasp on the object.

III. DISTRIBUTED COOPERATIVE MANIPULATION CONTROL STRATEGY

The distributed control strategy merges the swarm behavior obtained by implementing Reynolds' boids rules and a BSP controller implemented on each vehicle used to keep the distances. The swarm behavior models were constructed in accordance with the methodology suggested by the authors in [4]. The approach suggested in [11] was expanded and implemented in this work for robotic swarm control. The authors previously addressed the trajectory planning and control of a robotic 3D-printed manipulator that intentionally lacked joint feedback and executed actuation with poor joint accuracy in their earlier research on BSP (Belief Space Planning) [16], as well as in the motion planning of a marine companion robot for diver assistance and support [15]. Belief Space Planning methods enable the simultaneous reduction of uncertainty and

attainment of the desired state, as measured by the covariance of the state estimate measure. These attributes render them exceptionally well-suited for carrying out tasks in unstructured environments that are marked by substantial levels of noise. A vehicle's "Belief Space" trajectory transforms it from its present state (e.g., a specified position/orientation), which is mathematically represented as a Gaussian probability density function (PDF), to a target state PDF (Probability Density Function) that possesses the intended mean value and reduced covariance. Modeling the system state involves combining a signal component with a Gaussian noise component.

A sequence of segments in the belief space approximates linearly the trajectory that is intended for the vehicle. Direct transcription establishes the starting and ending locations of every segment. Such discretization method is summarized in Figure 2; for more details refer to [11] and [3].

Fig. 2: Direct Transcription is a special kind of Nonlinear Programming Optimization method. The control variables are discretized as piecewise-constant trajectories while the state variables are represented by linear segments. The optimization is performed by considering the discrete values of the variables representing the control and the state at each segment endpoint.

The algorithm traverses the trajectory of the Belief Space segment by segment and piecemeal. In order to transition from one segment extreme to the starting point of the subsequent segment, the necessary control actions are calculated using a Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR). The process is repeated on the linearized trajectory segments until the vehicle arrives at its ultimate destination in the belief space, which is denoted by a vector of Gaussian PDFs containing the intended

mean values for the end point and orientation, along with a diminished covariance of the expected measures for the point and orientation. At each step along a requested path, the vehicle controller receives the current reference trajectory point, which is utilized to control the robot at the specified intermediate position. The ultimate objective in the belief space is accomplished through the iterative execution of this procedure. The algorithm evaluates the adequacy of the current calculated intermediate end point of the computed segment of the plan to approach the final position at each iteration. If the intermediate point is deemed inadequate, the algorithm replans it. In our scenario, all companion autonomous vessels adhere to the same trajectory, along which the grasped object should be transported, and keep a predetermined distance (varying degrees of this distance are measured in terms of cross-track error and distance along the path).

Given that the goal of every action in the belief space is to reduce the observation covariance at the midway-points and the endpoint in order to move the robot to the desired position, these actions can be classified as information gathering actions (since they decrease the uncertainties regarding the vehicle’s position). The planning takes place in a state space that is inherently non-linear and has a greater number of dimensions than the physical state space; consequently, the resulting dynamic is considerably underactuated (since the belief space’s dimensions are smaller than the number of control inputs affecting the physical system). The assumption of maximal likelihood of observations simplifies the problem, as is the case in the current paper, our prior research, and [11]. The maximum likelihood assumption posits that the current state of the system is the most probable state based on previous observations and actions performed. This implies that the actions executed successfully accomplish their intended purpose, thereby guiding the system towards the desired state. Across a variety of application contexts, our simulations validate that this assumption is, on average, accurate. In [11] a formal proof is provided about its optimality under linear Gaussian process assumptions. Here, the observations $z_t \in Z$ of the distance between the goal and the vehicle position are modeled as a non linear stochastic function of the vector $x_t \in X$, representing the (not directly observed) state of the system and of the environment

$$z_t = g(x_t) + \xi \quad (1)$$

where g is a deterministic function of the measurement and ξ is a zero mean Gaussian noise with covariance W_t , dependent on the state. The deterministic function f links the new state to the older one under the control action u_t

$$x_{t+1} = f(x_t, u_t) \quad (2)$$

where f and g are assumed to be differentiable functions of x_t and u_t . The controller is assumed to know the state through a probabilistic density function $P(x)$. The parameters of such a distribution are the “belief state” $b_t = [m_t^T \ s_t^T]^T$, where m_t is the mean of the belief state and $s = [s_1^T, \dots, s_d^T]^T$ is

a vector composed by the d columns of the covariance matrix Σ . If a linear Gaussian dynamics is assumed, the belief state can be updated by rules of the form

$$x_{t+1} = A_t(x_t - m_t) + f(m_t, u_t) \quad (3a)$$

$$z_t = C_t(x_t - m_t) + g(f(m_t, u_t)) + \xi \quad (3b)$$

where A_t and C_t are the Jacobian matrices $A_t = \frac{\delta f}{\delta x}(m_t, u_t)$, $C_t = \frac{\delta g}{\delta x}(m_t)$. The Gaussian distribution is given by:

$$\Sigma_t : P(x) = \mathcal{N}(x/m_t, \Sigma_t) \quad (4)$$

In these hypotheses, and assuming maximum likelihood of the observations, it can be proved that it is possible to derive by iteration a series of segments with an associated set of control actions by minimizing the cost function J

$$J(b_{\tau:T}, u_{\tau:T}) = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i (\hat{n}_i^T \Sigma_i \hat{n}_i)^2 + \sum_{t=\tau}^{T-1} \tilde{m}_t^T Q \tilde{m}_t + \tilde{u}_t^T R \tilde{u}_t \quad (5)$$

where $b_{\tau:T}$ is the subset of the state space, $u_{\tau:T}$ are the corresponding actions for a given state space trajectory, Q and R are weight matrices, and the n_i are the versors of belief space along which the optimization is performed. Finally, Σ_T is the covariance matrix at the end of the segment, and m_t^T the value of the mean of the Gaussian of the measures. The function J is minimized by a standard SQP (Sequential Quadratic Programming) algorithm; after this, a linear quadratic regulator is applied to move along the segments.

The procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1. The BSP strategy needs to know the initial belief state and final goal b_0 and b_{goal} , and returns the sequence $u_{1:s}$ of the control actions. As a preliminary step all the variables of the algorithm are initialized to proper values via the function `InitBSP` (line 1 of Algorithm 1). The procedure is then executed for a predefined number of steps N . At each step, a plan is calculated via the `CreatePlan` function (line 3), obtaining the two sequences $(\tilde{m}_{1:s}, \tilde{u}_{1:s})$. This plan is executed for s steps; in case the planned steps do not converge to the final goal, variable k and counter r (line 13) are in charge of managing the eventual re-planning. In this phase, three values are calculated (lines 6-8): u_t is returned by the LQR control, while z_t is the noisy perceived position measurement (see equation (1)); finally the value m_{t+1} is propagated through an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF). If the resulting error between the mean of the current reference belief state \tilde{m}_t and the mean of the current belief state m_t is under a given threshold thr_1 (line 9), the algorithm sends the commands to the underlying vehicle low-level control system. The algorithm drives the robot, via the function `DriveVehicle`, towards the desired intermediate point in the trajectory (line 11), allowing the Cartesian error e_t to converge under a given threshold thr_2 (line 10). The function `DriveVehicle` returns as output the necessary vehicle trajectories η_t . Finally, if the error $\|\tilde{m}_t - m_t\|$ is greater

Algorithm 1: BSP Algorithm

Input : b_0, b_{goal} **Output:** $u_{1:s}$

```
1 initBSP ();
2 for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
3    $(\bar{m}_{1:s}, \bar{u}_{1:s}) = \text{CreatePlan}(m_0, m_{goal});$ 
4   for  $j = 1$  to  $s - k$  do
5      $k = r + j;$ 
6      $u_t = \text{LQR}(\bar{u}_t, \bar{m}_t, m_t);$ 
7      $z_t = g(x_t) + \xi;$ 
8      $m_{t+1} = \text{EKF}(m_t, u_t, z_t);$ 
9     if  $\|\bar{m}_t - m_t\| < thr_1$  then
10      while  $e_t > thr_2$  do
11         $\eta_t = \text{DriveVehicle}(m_t);$ 
12      else
13         $r = r + j - 1;$ 
```

than thr_1 , the counter r is updated in order to proceed with a necessary re-planning step (line 13).

The adoption of LQR standard control improves the efficiency of BSP planning: the evaluation of the optimal control action for the system leads to the stabilization of the trajectory in spite of the nonlinear dynamics of the system. Indeed, LQR control is able to handle small divergences from the planned motion, and thus minimizes the number of re-planning steps the system must calculate, improving in this way the computational efficiency. Previous experimental tests within a different application described in [16] showed that the statistical LQR calculation produces a decrease in computing time of about 70%. Hence, it is clear that the use of LQR in the algorithm leads to a smoother, and hence more efficient, motion of the robots.

The BSP approach is used with the Reynolds flocking model. Reynolds demonstrated in his publication [12] that flocking behaviors can be achieved by enforcing a remarkably uncomplicated set of rules on individual agents:

- 1) *Separation* — prevent the close proximity of neighboring objects through short-range repulsion.
- 2) *Alignment* — adjust direction to match the average heading of nearby agents.
- 3) *Cohesion* — direct towards the average position of neighboring entities (long-range attraction).

In our system, agents target the school of (robot) fishes center, which corresponds to the object to be grasped or transported, (rules 2, 3) and keep distance among themselves (rule 1).

The compliance of the robot which collectively grasp and transport the object (a passive member of the flock) allows our system to perform its tasks.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSION

The performed experiments focused on two different tasks requested to the swarm:

- *cooperative navigation*: the robots are required to navigate along a predefined path, keeping the norm of their task error (namely the distance of the vehicle with respect to the current point on the path) below a threshold, while at the same time avoiding collisions among them;
- *cooperative grasping*: the vehicles still have to navigate along the predefined path, while transporting the grasped object. This is obtained by imposing a further constraints on the minimization procedure: each robot should keep a distance from the object below another threshold. This condition comes from the fact that the robots exploits their smart deformable material to grasp the object, in a compliant and safe way.

The results of simulation relatively to the cooperative transportation phase are shown in Figure 3, where 3 companion robots follow a predefined path keeping a required formation, thanks to the BSP strategy on top of an extension of Reynolds' boids model, as explained in Section III. A better insight of the swarm behaviour is provided in Figure 4.

The depicted results have been obtained even in spite of an injection of additional noise on the swarm motion, confirming the feasibility and robustness of the approach. An example is depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 6 gives a glance on the evolution of the norm of vehicles mutual distances during the cooperative navigation mission. The threshold for vehicle distance to be kept has been defined equal to $1 m$, and this value is represented in Figure 6a by the orange horizontal line. In particular, note that the vehicles always avoid collisions among them and that the constraint on keeping $1 m$ among each others is violated only few times, precisely 25 times over 3579 samples (1193 samples for each of the 3 vehicles), meaning a violation of the constraint in about the 0.7% of the cases. This aspect deserves more investigation in future experiments, however this can easily be due to the fact that the vehicles are now simulated by the same CPU: the number of iterations at each sample time is kept low to limit the processing resources assigned to each vehicle and to avoid the time required for the simulation explode; it may happen that, at a certain step, the system could not find an optimal solution because the procedure reaches the maximum number of allowed iterations. In such a case, however, the system quickly recovers and the distance among the vehicles returns above the threshold. Probably, when implementing this control strategy on-board the single vehicles (each with a dedicated CPU), this situation will naturally not occur.

For the cooperative grasping phase, a constraint has been added in the optimization procedure: each vehicle has to keep its own distance from the object below a grasping threshold. This threshold has been set up equal to $0.8 m$, to simulate the grasping and transportation of a large, bulky object executed by small "tick-like" robots.

Figure 7 gives a glance on the evolution of the norm of vehicles distances from object during the cooperative grasping mission, where the pink horizontal line in Figure 7b represents the grasping threshold.

Fig. 3: Swarm with 3 companion robots performing a cooperative navigation for transportation.

Fig. 4: Insight of the swarm formation at selected instants of the path followed by the 3-vehicle swarm.

It is clear that the system succeeded in keeping the object grasped (by maintaining the distance of each vehicle from the object below the threshold); there are some outliers, namely in the 2.5% of the cases. From Figure 7, however, it is possible to conclude that this constraint violations are sparse in the mission execution, thus these outliers can be easily filtered out before sending the reference to the vehicles.

V. CONCLUSION

We developed a system that allows cooperative navigation and object grasping for a robotic swarm, whose behaviors are based on a BSP implementation of Reynolds' Boids. Our simulation runs show the viability of the approach, obtaining also a good result in vehicle collision avoidance.

In the future, we will develop and perform two-ways mixed reality simulation in order to refine the system design and we will then proceed to the implementation of real world swarms at field.

Our approach is scalable since we can manage more swarms with different companion vessels. We will also consider the implementation of the BSP swarming approach to a fleet of leader vessels and other approaches based on Gaussian Processes and information gain.

A hybrid layered approach will be adopted integrating, in a complementary way, distributed impedance control for grasping, Belief Space Planning for collective movement of the agents and Deep Learning for control optimization and

Fig. 5: Example of injected noise on vehicle 1 during cooperative navigation.

object recognition.

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(a) Boxplot representing the norm of the mutual distances among vehicles.

(b) Norm distribution of the mutual distances among vehicles during the mission execution.

Fig. 6: Details about swarm execution of cooperative transportation.

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(b) Norm distribution of the mutual distances among vehicles during the mission execution.

Fig. 7: Details about swarm execution of cooperative grasping.